

HDC8192: A General Purpose Mixed-Signal CMOS Architecture for Massively Parallel Hyperdimensional Computing

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Abstract—This paper addresses a mixed-mode CMOS circuit for Hyperdimensional Computing (HDC). HDC is based on the use of binary vectors with thousands dimensions to represent data in a holistic way. During the last years HDC has shown to be a powerful approach to solve classification problems. The proposed circuit architecture in this paper is made up of an array of 128×64 (8192) processing units (PUs) with a 1-bit ALU, local memory and connectivity to their 4 nearest neighbors to run the basic operations of HDC, i.e, binding, bundling and permutation. The architecture also includes a module to calculate Hamming distance to address classification. Post-layout simulations of the complete system working on various basic operations in $0.18 \mu\text{m}$ CMOS technology are shown.

Index Terms—Hyperdimensional computing, mixed-signal, associative memory, classification, CMOS

I. INTRODUCTION

Hyperdimensional computing (HDC) is a brain-inspired computing paradigm built on vectors in the thousands of dimensions to represent data, [1]. In the last years, HDC has addressed classification problems [2], [3], [4], [5], showing promising results compared to state-of-the-art deep learning algorithms. HDC computing involves simple operations, which makes it suitable for low-power hardware implementations.

We have designed a novel mixed-mode CMOS architecture to compute HDC algorithms taking into account the constraint of low-power consumption. The architecture comprises an array of 128×64 processing units (PUs) that perform the basic HDC operations. Our approach brings about two main novelties.

First, a local SRAM memory in each PU implements the associative memory needed in HDC algorithms, which makes in-PUs operations faster than its off-PU memory counterpart.

Second, the mixed-mode architecture simplifies the HDC operations of majority rule and Hamming distance calculation

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101016734. This work was also funded by Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities under grant RTI2018-097088-B-C32, from Xunta de Galicia-Consellería de Cultura, Educación e Ordenación Universitaria Accreditation 2019-2022 ED431G-2019/04 and Reference Competitive Group Accreditation 2021-2024 ED431C2021/048, co-funded by (ERDF/FEDER programme).

by means of analog circuitry, leading to less area than fully-digital implementations [6], [7], [8], [9].

The paper is outlined as follows. In Section II a brief introduction to the basics of HDC is made. Section III addressed the proposed mixed-signal CMOS system architecture for HDC computing. In Section IV the circuitry that implements HDC operations is discussed. Section V shows post-layout simulations of the PU array. Finally, Section VI addresses the conclusions and future work.

II. HYPERDIMENSIONAL COMPUTING PRIMITIVES

As mentioned above, HDC is a brain-inspired computing paradigm in which low-dimensional data, such image features, signal values, data text etc., are mapped into a vector with thousands of components. In this way, the information contained in the low-dimensional data is spread along thousands of components. This work tackles HDC vectors with 8192 components or dimensions, which is in line with other today CMOS hardware proposals [9]. The mapping into an HD-vector (HDV) is made through an HD encoder that provides the holistic representation of the low-dimensional data, assigning orthogonal HDVs to dissimilar low-dimensional inputs. The use of associative memory (AM), [1], wherein the data is retrieved by comparing a query HDV with memory data content, is also a key component of HDC classification algorithms.

HDC comprises three basic primitives, i.e., binding, bundling and permutation.

Binding two binary HDVs, \mathbf{V}_1 and \mathbf{V}_2 generates a dissimilar HDV, i.e. an HDV orthogonal to \mathbf{V}_1 and \mathbf{V}_2 . Binary HDV binding is carried out with a bit-wise XOR Boolean gate between two HDC vectors \mathbf{V}_1 and \mathbf{V}_2 :

$$\mathbf{V}_1 = 010100\dots00$$

$$\mathbf{V}_2 = 110110\dots10$$

$$\mathbf{V}_1 * \mathbf{V}_2 = 100010\dots10$$

The second basic operation is bundling of two or more HDVs, run during on-line training to generate a class vector

representing the complete set of HDVs in the class. In the case of binary HDVs, bundling is implemented with the majority rule, which is a bit-wise function that assigns the most frequent logic value for a given bit position among the input HDVs to the corresponding bit position in the output HDV, as shown in the following example:

$$\begin{array}{r}
 \mathbf{V}_1 = 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ \dots\ 0\ 0 \\
 \mathbf{V}_2 = 1\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1\ 0\ \dots\ 1\ 0 \\
 \mathbf{V}_3 = 0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ 1\ \dots\ 0\ 1 \\
 \mathbf{V}_4 = 1\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 1\ 0\ 0\ \dots\ 1\ 0 \\
 \text{---} \\
 \mathbf{V}_1 + \mathbf{V}_2 + \mathbf{V}_3 + \mathbf{V}_4 = 1\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 0\ \dots\ 1\ 0
 \end{array}$$

The last operation is permutation, which rotates the components of the HDV by a given number of positions suitable for encoding several HDVs into a meaningful HDV for classification tasks.

The classification process is carried out by comparing query HDVs with those stored in an associative memory (AM) through Hamming distance [1]:

$$\text{Hamming distance} = \sum_{i=1}^N \mathbf{V}_1(i) \text{ XOR } \mathbf{V}_{\text{am}}(i)$$

where N is the number of components of the HDV, \mathbf{V}_1 is the query HDV and \mathbf{V}_{am} is the HDV read from the AM which represents a class. The \mathbf{V}_{am} HDV with the minimum Hamming distance gives the class of \mathbf{V}_1 HDV.

Binding and bundling include operations between the same components of the HDV, whereas permutation and Hamming distance calculation involve operations between different HDV components. To reduce data flow, and therefore power consumption, and to increase speed, our proposal in this paper is an architecture with a 2D array of PUs with their own memory, and locally connected to their four nearest neighbors. Altogether allows to run the three HDC operators, i.e., binding, bundling and permutation.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

The system core has 8192 Processing Units (PUs) distributed in a 128×64 array, where all of them receive the same controls signals following a Single Instruction Multiple Data (SIMD) approach. Every PU has local processing capabilities through a 1-bit ALU and it is connected to their four nearest neighbors, as shown in Fig. 1, following an x-y torus architecture. This scheme allows to move data along both horizontal and vertical axis, which can be used for different purposes. One of them is to implement circular shifts in both directions, widely used in common hyperdimensional computing algorithms, by connecting the last PU in each row with the first one in the next row. Also, connectivity in the y-axis permits to implement random shifts extremely faster than with only communication in the horizontal axis. For instance, a 256 right shift could be executed with 4 down shifts instead of 256 circular shifts.

Fig. 1. I/O scheme and system architecture of HDC8192.

Another important application of the PU's 4-connectivity is the data input/output to the system. With the use of multiplexers at the bottom row (see Fig. 1) it is possible to introduce 64 bits coming from the outside into the system. These data can then be moved into the next row in the same clock cycle as a new stream of 64 bits is inserted into the bottom row. With this, the hyperprocessor will be loaded with the desired hypervector after 128 clock cycles at most. The same strategy can be used to read out a stored hypervector from the top row.

IV. CIRCUITS IMPLEMENTATION

Each PU must include all the circuitry required for common hyperdimensional computing operations while maintaining a small pitch for a feasible implementation of the 128×64 array. Thus, a 1-bit ALU such as the one shown in Fig. 2 is designed, where the logic unit is implemented with an NOR gate, which provides functional completeness, with latched inputs and tri-state output connected to the PU's own bus, or to any of the buses of their nearest four neighbors. Also, to increase the versatility of the design, the latches' inputs can collect data from the bus either as they are or their inverted version with the inclusion of an inverter and a multiplexer. The 1-bit ALU and the local memory allow to run any digital function, and thus HDC operations, provided the correct sequence of control signals.

Communication between PUs is carried out through the tri-state buffers driven by the NOR gate. Each of them is connected to one neighbor's bus. Directions E and W are used for one position circular shifts by enabling their corresponding buffers. When that occurs, its selected neighbor bus will be loaded with NOR gate's output, which can be then written into a processor latch or to neighbors SRAM.

Fig. 2. PU schematic formed by the logic unit at the bottom part, a 16-bit SRAM, a majority rule block and a current source.

Fig. 3. Majority rule block used in each PU of HDC8192.

All the information across the PUs is shared through a common 1-bit bus, connected to all the functional blocks. For the information storage, a custom-made 16-bit 6T-SRAM is included, with an array of 4×4 bits. Each SRAM's column and row receive a control signals from the chip periphery in a one-hot format, avoiding the use of PU-level decoders. As it is a 1-bit processor, only 1 bit can be written or read per clock cycle. Additionally, the two first columns of the SRAM serve to a double purpose. The first one is to hold general information as the other bits of the SRAM, and the second one is to buffer the input to the majority rule block.

To calculate the result of the majority rule on a set of n hypervectors with $n \leq 8$, the majority rule block writes the stored values from the SRAM memory into eight MiM capacitors through NMOS transistors using signal *write_MA*, as shown in Fig. 3. At the same time, the node V_A is charged to voltage $v_{precharge}$ to improve circuit's yield by loading the parasitic input capacitance of the first inverter with a selected voltage. This voltage can be used also for biasing the output value, which is useful to decide the tie case outcome (four ones and four zeros). After the input is written to the capacitors, they are all shorted with signal *e_MA* and their average value stored at node V_A . In addition, the first tri-state inverter is activated, setting the output to the inverted desired output. This inverter is used as a comparator and it was designed

Fig. 4. Processing unit of the HDC8192 layout with its parts labeled.

to cope with the effect of non-ideal switches implemented with NMOS transistors, which, in our implementation, due to their threshold voltage will shift down logic '1' representation from 1.8 V to approximately 1.15 V. Therefore, it was sized to have its threshold at 575 mV which corresponds to the voltage generated by four '0's and four '1's read out from the 16-bit SRAM. Finally, to circumvent the low gain of the first inverter caused by the threshold voltage modification, a second tri-state inverter is added with feedback loop to V_A , which is turned on with *read_MA* after *out* signal is settled.

One common operation in hyperdimensional computing is Hamming distance between two hypervectors to find the closest profile to a query hypervector. One possible option for this could be just to execute the XOR operation between each component of the hypervector at each PU and send the resultant hypervector to digital circuitry located at the periphery to count the number of ones. This approach would require an additional digital block and to move all the data from the PU array to the periphery, with the corresponding increase in area, processing time and energy consumption. In this work, a different strategy is applied: by adding a current source implemented with an NMOS transistor biased with a current mirror it is possible to obtain a current proportional to the number of ones after the XOR operation is executed. This current source has two enable transistors controlled by the control signal e_I and by the BUS voltage, and it has its output connected to a column bus that gathers the current from all PUs of a column. These column buses are also connected between them, summing up all the currents from the array of PUs. Thus, after the XOR operation this current source is enabled and only those where the result was one will add its current.

All these circuitry were designed and laid out in a 180 nm CMOS technology with 1.8 V as power supply. Fig. 4 shows the resulting layout, where the main parts of the PU can be seen, occupying an area of $20.8 \times 44 \mu\text{m}^2$. The 16-bit SRAM memory, as well as the current output source and the majority rule block, were laid out manually in a full-custom approach. On the other hand, due to its fully-digital nature, the logic unit was laid out using standard cells from the technology's design kit. A 128×64 PUs array was built, connected between them as described in Section III, with the input logic at the bottom and the output logic at the top, as shown in the chip layout of

Fig. 5. HDC8192 chip labeled layout. This chip occupies $3.3 \times 3.3 \text{ mm}^2$ in a 180 nm CMOS technology.

Fig. 5. The total chip area is $3.3 \times 3.3 \text{ mm}^2$.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section shows different post-layout simulations of the circuits designed in this work. The first one corresponds to the majority rule block. To test this circuit, the post-layout model of the PU was used to take into account all possible parasitic effects on the result. This test was performed with a clock frequency of 50 MHz to generate control signals, such as the ones responsible to load the input vectors in the SRAM or the signals needed in the majority rule block. All possible options were included in the simulation, with a test vector containing from zero to eight ones. The results are shown in Fig. 6 accompanied by their control signals. In the middle plot we can see the voltage at node V_A , that goes to $v_{precharge}$ while the capacitors are being loaded to the input signals when $write_MA$ is high. Then, $read_MA$ goes high and shorts all the capacitors together into the V_A node. Finally, signal $read_MA$ turns on the feedback loop charging or discharging the node V_A as a function of the final result.

To test the remainder blocks of the PU and the functionality at system level, a post-layout simulation of a small array of 4×4 PUs following the architecture of Fig. 1 was executed. In this simulation, the Hamming distance of two different vectors, namely, \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} , was computed with the sum of currents from each PU. Vector \mathbf{A} was all ones for all the cases, and vector \mathbf{B} ranged from all zeros to all ones going through all possible options in between.

To compute the Hamming distance between \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} it is first necessary to calculate the bitwise XOR between them. This is done at each PU using NOR logic implementing:

$$\mathbf{A} \text{ XOR } \mathbf{B} = (\bar{\mathbf{A}} \text{ NOR } \bar{\mathbf{B}}) \text{ NOR } (\mathbf{A} \text{ NOR } \mathbf{B})$$

Thus, after loading \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{B} into the PUs array, the XOR operation is computed in seven clock cycles. Then, the result is loaded into each PU's bus and the current source enabled,

Fig. 6. Majority rule block post-layout simulation for different number of ones in the input vector.

Fig. 7. Current output from a Hamming distance between two 16-bit vectors, with error bars representing Monte Carlo variation scaled up by a factor of 10 \times , and its corresponding error with respect to the ideal output.

summing all the currents in a single bus. The results of this simulation for all possible values of \mathbf{B} are shown in Fig. 7, where a biasing current of 55 nA was selected for the current sources as a tradeoff between accuracy and power consumption.

VI. OUTLOOK & CONCLUSIONS

This paper has presented a novel architecture and the preliminary results of a CMOS mixed-signal chip for HDC. The system comprises an array of 128×64 PUs that performs the HDC operations. The main contributions of the chip are two. The first one is the introduction of local SRAM memory in each PU, thus reducing the data flow and therefore power consumption. The second contribution is the use of analog circuitry to carry out Hamming distance calculation and majority rule, simplifying the circuitry and reducing area compared to their digital counterpart implementation. Experimental results will be shown at conference if available.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Kanerva, "Hyperdimensional computing: An introduction to computing in distributed representation with high-dimensional random vectors," *Cognitive computation*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 139–159, 2009.
- [2] A. Rahimi, S. Benatti, P. Kanerva, L. Benini, and J. M. Rabaey, "Hyperdimensional biosignal processing: A case study for emg-based hand gesture recognition," in *2016 IEEE International Conference on Rebooting Computing (ICRC)*, pp. 1–8, 2016.
- [3] A. Rahimi, P. Kanerva, L. Benini, and J. M. Rabaey, "Efficient biosignal processing using hyperdimensional computing: Network templates for combined learning and classification of exg signals," *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 1, pp. 123–143, 2019.
- [4] L. Ge and K. K. Parhi, "Classification using hyperdimensional computing: A review," *IEEE Circuits and Systems Magazine*, vol. 20, pp. 30–47, 2020.
- [5] A. Joshi, J. T. Halseth, and P. Kanerva, "Language geometry using random indexing," in *Quantum Interaction* (J. A. de Barros, B. Coecke, and E. Pothos, eds.), pp. 265–274, Springer International Publishing, 2017.
- [6] A. Rahimi, S. Datta, D. Kleyko, E. P. Frady, B. Olshausen, P. Kanerva, and J. M. Rabaey, "High-dimensional computing as a nanoscalable paradigm," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 64, no. 9, pp. 2508–2521, 2017.
- [7] M. Schmuck, L. Benini, and A. Rahimi, "Hardware optimizations of dense binary hyperdimensional computing: Rematerialization of hyper-vectors, binarized bundling, and combinational associative memory," *J. Emerg. Technol. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 15, Oct. 2019.
- [8] S. Salamat, M. Imani, and T. Rosing, "Accelerating hyperdimensional computing on fpgas by exploiting computational reuse," *IEEE Transactions on Computers*, vol. 69, no. 8, pp. 1159–1171, 2020.
- [9] M. Eggimann, A. Rahimi, and L. Benini, "A 5 μ w standard cell memory-based configurable hyperdimensional computing accelerator for always-on smart sensing," *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems I: Regular Papers*, vol. 68, no. 10, pp. 4116–4128, 2021.